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Author: Bradley Johnson
ORCID: Unassigned
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American Monolingualism as a Strategic Disadvantage in Counterintelligence

***Abstract:** Widespread monolingualism in America creates a major blindspot in counterintelligence. Many may view this as completely acceptable as English, America's first and legal language, is the most spoken and most learned language in the world. Despite this, none of our adversaries have English as their first language, and they are not keen on using English for their internal communication. Our adversaries will, however, use English as a tool for information operations and espionage in the United States to a level that we are utterly incapable of matching. Russia, China, North Korea and Iran all have advanced intelligence capabilities, and Russia, China, and Iran have a large population of English speakers. Therefore, there must be a sizable, intelligent population of Americans who speak their languages to defeat them in the intelligence sphere. In order to stop our adversaries from taking advantage of America's monolingualism and committing acts of espionage, information warfare, and other intelligence operations against the American people, The United States' educational apparatus must support increased efforts to promote language learning among young people.*

***Keywords:** American Monolingualism; Counterintelligence; Foreign Language Proficiency; Intelligence Workforce Development; Strategic Vulnerabilities; Information Operations; Espionage; Cognitive Security; Adversary Intelligence Services; Russia; China; Iran; North Korea; Linguistic Capability Gaps; National Security Education; Intelligence Tradecraft; Strategic Competition; Language Policy*

Americans speak the world's current lingua franca. This is great news for young Americans looking to do business internationally. Unfortunately, this creates a sense of complacency with regards to our language learning infrastructure^[1]. This complacency has meant that the vast majority of Americans are monolingual. According to the American Academy of Arts and Sciences, almost 80% of Americans speak only one language^[2]. Not only are the vast majority of Americans monolingual, but a huge share of our bilingual and polyglot population are immigrants and their children, many of whom are already middle aged or older.^{[3][4]} Additionally, many of these immigrants are not citizens, and would have a very difficult time being eligible for work in the intelligence services. Even relying on immigrant populations,

¹ Altschuler and Wippman, "How Many People are Monolingual"

² Altschuler and Wippman, "How Many People are Monolingual"

³ Dietrich and Hernandez, "What Languages Do We Speak in the United States"

⁴ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States," 3.

especially their children, the reality is that the form of their heritage language that they speak will be perceptibly different from the current versions of their languages in their ‘home’ countries. Exposure to a very different language for the vast majority of someone’s life with exposure of the heritage language coming through the colloquial language of their parents and not from academic or standard sources will also lead to significant differences between young immigrants’ versions of their languages when compared to the more academic or professional versions of their languages^{[5][6]}. America’s intelligence services must have a population of proficient operatives that can speak modern and proper versions of these languages.

Counterintelligence focuses on protecting the United States from intelligence operations orchestrated by foreign adversaries who all speak and operate in a variety of languages. Civilians in adversarial countries learn English at high rates and can use it for both economic and national security reasons. Learning foreign languages is extremely important in day-to-day intelligence operations. The CIA lists a variety of operations and tasks in which language knowledge is extremely important: open source research, human source collection, analysis of economic reports, ideological research on adversarial leaders, and analysis of local press.^[7] How can an operative recruit sources if he cannot understand them and they cannot understand him? How can rapport be built if cultural nuances are not understood, as the method by which they are conveyed is poorly known by the operative? For example, Mandarin is a tonal language with 4 tones. A word can have four different meanings depending on the tones of voice. The word for teacher is *lǎoshī* but if one were to say *lǎoshǐ*, it would mean “old shit.” If an operative called a cutting-edge science researcher and high-value target “old shit,” one can easily imagine the fallout. In the same arena is analysis of open source and classified intelligence. Farsi, Russian, Arabic, Chinese, and Korean use different writing methods. If an American who is only familiar with the Latin script attempts to read a Farsi article, it would be completely impossible. Furthermore, the Chinese put out a very large stream of press releases with complex Chinese versions and shorter, simpler English versions that are usually just the abstract. An excellent example of this is in their national security whitepaper released in the late spring of 2025.^{[8][9]} China is able to give the US Intelligence Community a sterilized and useless understanding of the Chinese doctrine for guaranteeing their own national security. All the while, China is able to signal to their own security apparatus and their own intelligence apparatus what exactly their aims are. If America is unable to translate China’s full doctrine, how can the United States hope to stop it? Language is still integral to intelligence gathering, and none of the intricacies of language and culture are ever going away. If the United States’ Intelligence Community cannot

⁵ Harris, Miglio, and Gries, “Mexican and Chicano Spanish Prosody,” 5-9.

⁶ Dubnina and Polinsky, “Russian in the US,” 11-15.

⁷ CIA, “Language Capability in the Intelligence Community,” 1-4.

⁸ State Council Information Office of the People’s Republic of China, “Abstract of White Paper on China’s National Security in a New Era” (English)

⁹ State Council Information Office of the People’s Republic of China, “China’s National Security in a New Era” (Mandarin)

perform these integral tasks quickly and accurately, then it will lose the upper hand and provide our adversaries a significant advantage. In order to understand the magnitude of this problem, it is necessary to analyze the raw numbers on the differences in speakers from America's adversaries versus the homeland itself.

China

Beginning a journey from adversary to adversary, it would be most useful to begin with the most powerful, China. China's most spoken and primary language is Mandarin. Mandarin is a language with 3.5 million speakers in the United States.^[10] This is a great deal more than any other language regarding the big 4: China, Russia, Iran, and North Korea. With 3.5 million Mandarin Chinese speakers, there is a sizable population to draw from. Unfortunately, that population mostly consists of immigrants and their children who may not be citizens or may be too old to retrain into a national security focused field. Despite the fact that most of America's current Mandarin speakers are not eligible or able to serve in counterintelligence roles, they are still able to teach their language to the next generation. China is the second largest economy in the world making Mandarin an advantageous language to learn for intelligence personnel and civilians alike. Still, a concerted effort must be made. Young Americans who do not grow up in Mandarin speaking households should also have the ability to learn the language. Mandarin Chinese is a language with immense upside and a native speaker population large enough to teach it to a generation of young Americans.

To contrast American numbers of Chinese speakers with the number of Chinese English speakers reveals just how much concerted effort in language learning can produce. This is in a country that, like the United States, does not do very well in foreign language studies. China has 1.4 billion people against America's 340 million. This comparison is not necessarily fair given this ratio, but the effect produced exists irrespective of this lack of mathematical fairness. According to Rining and Su 2012, 93.8% of the 415.95 million foreign language learners in China studied English, meaning that 390.16 million Mainland Chinese had learned or had been learning English in the year 2000. 1.8%, or 7.02 million, of those 390 million were of interpreter quality, with 3.53%, or 13.77 million, as fluent but not professional speakers, and 15.61%, or 61 million, were conversational^[11]. This means that even if all of the United States' 3.5 million fluent Chinese speakers could speak at an interpreter level, China's English speakers would still double America's Mandarin speakers. Additionally, China had a population of conversational English speakers larger than the population of Italy 25 years ago. The United States is, indeed, terribly behind China in proficiency. It is likely that many more Chinese, now with ready access to their form of internet, can speak English to a fluent or conversational degree. In 2000, there

¹⁰ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States," 3.

¹¹ Rining and Su, "The Statistics of English in China"

were more English learners in China than there are Americans today. If the Chinese Ministry of State Security needs to find an English speaker, they need to just walk outside.

To give an example of the difficulties the United States has had with Mandarin over the past few years, we need look no farther than in our diplomatic efforts. In 2021, The US and China engaged in talks in Alaska that turned sour quickly with direct sparring between Chinese and American diplomats. What made matters worse is that the American translator repeatedly made grievous errors and led to increased hostility. The American translator made 6 errors throughout the talks that directly resulted in increasing tensions between both parties before the talks devolved into a shouting match. Conversely, the Chinese translator only made 1 error, which actually softened the blow of an aggressive statement made by a Chinese diplomat.^[12] The United States, even in extremely important high-pressure situations, cannot rely on its language experts to deliver proper translations. If this can happen in a highly important diplomatic meeting, it can certainly happen when gathering or analyzing Chinese intelligence.

Russia

Connected to China through the vast expanse of Siberia is the Russian Federation, an adversary of the United States for over 100 years. With regards to America's Russian speaking population, there are a fair few Russian speakers at around 940,000. The vast majority of these speakers, as is the case with Mandarin, are immigrants and their children. Immigration from Russia has come in many waves, with the largest being in the 20-year span between 1990 and 2010 with over 600,000.^[13] Interestingly, Russian speakers came to the United States in their largest numbers when the cold war ended while the State Department shifted its eyes away from Russia. Nonetheless, these relatively recent arrivals do generously pad the numbers. Russian language education is currently in tatters with an ever decreasing number of programs and an almost complete absence in high schools.^[14] With an ever-decreasing amount of infrastructure built for the learning of Russian, there are few encouraging signs for the continued increase in Russian speakers in the United States without continued immigration from Russian speaking countries.

With America's nearly 1 million Russian speakers, how does Russia compare in their number of English speakers? Similarly to China, there is no real equivalence. According to Rubcova, Pavenkov, and Pavenkov, 11% of Russians can speak English freely and as many as 22% of young Russians can speak English freely. This translates to 16.7 million Russians who can speak English freely^[15]. With less than half the population of the United States, the Russians have a much greater number of English speakers than America has Russian speakers. Although

¹² Zhou, "What the American Interpreter Got Wrong in US-China Talks"

¹³ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States," 3.

¹⁴ Shteinert, "Know Your Enemy's Face"

¹⁵ Rubcova, Pavenkov, and Pavenkov, "English, Russian, and Russian English in Russia"

both personal and anecdotal, I traveled to Russia in the summer of 2017. In the cities of Moscow and St. Petersburg, basically every internationally facing person spoke English with a level of proficiency that would mirror a native speaker. There is no shortage of English speaking Russians. The SVR, the Russian foreign intelligence service, could, like the MSS, the Chinese foreign intelligence service, simply walk to a local coffee shop and find an English speaker. The same cannot be said about the CIA finding a Russian speaker.

To give an example of Russia's capabilities in running operations against the United States, one must only look at the nature of our political discourse. Much of the messaging in Right vs Left political discourse is actually engineered by the Russian Federation. In fact, Russia has been so successful at campaigns against Americans that they were able to pay 6 American conservative pundits to spout Kremlin backed views on Ukraine and the US government. This operation was so successful that many of these pundits even claimed that they did not know the people paying them were Russian.^[16] How would these pundits not know that they are being paid by Russians? It is likely that the people paying them were instructing them on what to say in perfect or near perfect English. Language can be a weapon when used correctly and by the right people. The Russians have used this to great effect. In all, Russia boasts a large English speaking population, far more than America's Russian speaking population, and has exercised their ability to use it to influence American politics.

Iran

From Russia, moving south through central Asia, one arrives at the Islamic Republic of Iran, a large sponsor of global terror and a country against whom the United States has taken military action. Iran also organizes chants of "Death to America," and they describe the United States as "the Great Satan." In Iran, the primary language is Farsi, a language with few speakers in the United States. The United States possesses fewer than 500,000 Farsi speakers.^[17] All of these speakers are likely immigrants and their children. Additionally, there are no Farsi schools nor are there Farsi language programs in high schools around the country. It is likely that, unless there be a surge of immigration from Central Asia, that number would slowly decline generation to generation. To make matters worse, Farsi language programs would likely be unpopular as the only countries which have Farsi, or its Afghan counterpart Dari, as official languages are Iran and Afghanistan.^[18] If the American intelligence community desperately needed someone to decipher something from Farsi, they would be essentially compelled to contract that out to a linguist.

Iran, despite not being a current or recent economic powerhouse, still is part of the big 4 intelligence adversaries, and they are no slouch when it comes to language learning. Iran is an

¹⁶ Suderman and Swenson, "Right Wing Influencers were Duped to Work for Covert Russian Operation"

¹⁷ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States," 3.

¹⁸ University of Pennsylvania, "Persian | Penn Language Center"

already multilingual country. Only roughly 50% of Iranians speak Farsi as their first language.^[19] However, it is still the language of government and media, and it is generally well understood by the vast majority of Iranians. Alongside this propensity to have to learn a neighbor's language, Iranians also are compelled to learn another language in school. Until recently, that language was English. Now, however, Iranian children can choose between English and some other Western languages and are compelled to learn Arabic, the language of the holy Qur'an.^[20] This effectively means that nearly every Iranian has some familiarity with English. Whether that be fluency or something as basic as recognizing and knowing the Latin script, some familiarity is always better than complete ignorance. Education First's English Proficiency Index counts Iran as having low English proficiency, but only 1 point off moderate. That being higher than Mexico, Brazil, China, and Japan^[21]. The exact numbers of English speakers in Iran is not clear, but given these metrics, there are still likely more English speakers in Iran as there are Farsi Speakers in the United States. The largest group of English speakers in Iran are young, and even though those under 21 are not as proficient as those between 21 and 25.^[22] There is still a great potential in Iran to continue to improve their English proficiency.

When considering intelligence failures that have *already* happened as a result of an inability to translate documents and collect intelligence in Iran, 1979 comes to mind. In 1979, the CIA was entirely dependent on the Shah's intelligence service, SAVAK, for their information on the country. SAVAK was unwilling to provide the CIA with information revealing instability, so the assumption was made that there was not any. There was an understanding between the CIA, the Shah, and SAVAK that any interaction with the enemies of the Shah by the CIA would be seen as weakness and should never be done. This was argued under the auspices of cultural sensitivities.^[23] Even if the United States wanted to conduct intelligence without the help of SAVAK, there would have been difficulty with covert operatives trying to blend in. After all, there were very few CIA operatives with any knowledge of Farsi or Arabic at the time.^[24] Even on the diplomatic side, only 3 individuals in the Ambassador's staff had experience with Farsi. This led to an American presence in Iran that could not predict and avert the fall of the Shah.^[25] Conversely, the Israelis had full knowledge of the situation in Iran thanks to a large number of Persian, Farsi speaking Jews working for the Mossad. This meant that the Israelis were actually able to "sense" the tension brewing in Iran.^[26] America's failure was multifaceted, but it is clear that, when an intelligence service has the capacity to conduct their own human intelligence and

¹⁹ University of Pennsylvania, "Persian | Penn Language Center"

²⁰ Shahriari, "The Status of English in Iran," 1-3.

²¹ Education First, "Iran | EF English Proficiency Index"

²² Education First, "Iran | EF English Proficiency Index"

²³ Sweet, "Intelligence Agencies Under Fire", 5-6.

²⁴ Moscoe, "Iran 1978-1979: Reflections on Intelligence Failure"

²⁵ Sweet, "Intelligence Agencies Under Fire", 5-6.

²⁶ Moscoe, "Iran 1978-1979: Reflections on Intelligence Failure"

source collection thanks to having operatives who speak the local language, intelligence failures can be averted. Nonetheless, Iran is now an adversary, and one with many English speakers.

Arab World

Across the Zagros Mountains and into Mesopotamia and beyond lies the Arab world. There are a vast number of countries with Arabic as a primary language with whom the United States has been, and will continue to be, in protracted conflict. There is hope for Arabic in the United States as there are quite a few native speakers, and nearly a quarter of them are young.^{[27][28]} This basically means that there is a large quantity of people who could be potentially recruited to serve in an intelligence role. According to Pew polling, there are 1.45 million Arabic Speakers in the United States currently, and according to the Census Bureau, in 2021 23.8% of the at-home Arabic speakers were under 20 years old.^{[29][30][31]} This is a good start to be sure, but there is so much territory to cover for those young Arabic speakers. With several Active conflict zones including Israel/Palestine, Sudan, Syria, Libya, Yemen, and Morocco/Western Sahara, there is a vast need to fill with regards to active intelligence and counterintelligence in these arenas. What makes this somewhat concerning is the reality that the United States has been militarily engaged in the Middle East constantly since 2001 with wars occurring off and on before then. Still, with all this experience and decades of war, the United States still does not teach Arabic with any real vigor.

There is a little more good news when it comes to English proficiency in the Middle East, as there is not much proficiency there at all. Education First's English Proficiency Index has every country in the Middle East except Israel and Iran as being quite poor regarding English proficiency.^[32] Even if the American intelligence services cannot decipher Arabic without shoddy tech tools or hiring a linguist, every single Arabic speaking country is in the same predicament.

North Korea

Korean is the one language the United States can assume a linguistic advantage. North Korea makes outside information completely inaccessible, and it would be foolish to assume that anyone outside of particular party members would ever be allowed to interact with English. Additionally, the United States has a large Korean community. There are over 1 million people who speak Korean at home.^[33] It can be easily assumed that the Juche Hermit Kingdom does not have anywhere near 1 million speakers of English. Another advantage comes through South

²⁷ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States," 3.

²⁸ Dietrich and Hernandez, "What Languages Do We Speak in the United States"

²⁹ Moslimani, "Facts About Arabic Speakers"

³⁰ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States," 3.

³¹ Dietrich and Hernandez, "What Languages Do We Speak in the United States"

³² Education First, EF English Proficiency Index"

³³ Census Bureau, "Language Use in the United States", 3.

Korea, a staunch American ally. Millions of South Koreans and the South Korean intelligence apparatus can be used to supplement any deficiency the United States may have. North Korea has still launched successful intelligence operations in the United States, especially with regards to the hacking of Sony Pictures after the production of the film, “The Interview.”^[34] North Korea was able to warn Sony that this was going to happen, giving Sony the ability to try to stop it, then executed the attack anyway. The North Koreans do have the ability to hack Western, or in this case Japanese, media companies as retribution for poor depictions of Kim Jong Un. This does speak to North Korea’s ability to launch operations against the United States, Japan, South Korea, and others. If North Korea can successfully breach the security of a multi-billion dollar media giant despite giving said media giant forewarning, what could they do to more critical companies like water, power, internet service, healthcare, and transportation providers without forewarning? Despite this, North Korea has an uphill battle if they ever want to out do the United States in terms of language proficiency.

The Solution

In the majority of our mission critical language proficiencies, we are at worst far behind and at best bailed out by allies and Juche totalitarianism. The speakers we have are of immigrant communities who may have trouble getting clearances, and their children may not speak their language to a proper or professional level, meaning even they would need to take language courses. Given this problem, what is the best way to fix the problem? Finding an ideal solution to America’s language deficiencies is difficult, especially when trying to balance cost and accessibility with effectiveness. A good solution must be inexpensive and effective to be useful. These programs should focus on language learning for children and young adults. Language acquisition occurs at a far quicker rate among young people and the fact that adults seldom have the spare time to learn a language effectively. In order to understand what the best course of action may be, there must first be an analysis of who ought to do the learning, then popular, but unfeasible options before addressing the best option available.

It is highly important to focus on America’s children and young adults when it comes to Language Education. Language acquisition and accuracy over a long period of learning slowly declines after the age of 17.4 years old. This is considerably later than the peak age of ultimate attainment, but still puts the best time to learn a language well before adulthood.^[35] Ultimate attainment is less important than just being very good at a language for almost all applications, so it would be most effective for the target demographic to be children and teenagers.

Immersion programs may be the most effective, but they are also the most expensive. Middlebury Language Schools is considered to be among the best, if not the absolute best when it comes to teaching languages to people in an immersive setting. The language pledge and the

³⁴ Steinberg, Stepan, and Neary, “The Hacking of Sony Pictures”

³⁵ Hartshorne, Tenenbaum, and Pinker, “A Critical Period for Second Language Acquisition”

focus on exclusively living in the language of study does present significant improvement in language capability in a very short time. The biggest issue with their program is its completely unattainable cost for the average American. A Middlebury summer language program for Chinese costs \$15,580 for education and accommodation.^[36] Cheaper options than Middlebury certainly exist. For example, Concordia Language Villages has High School Credit language programs for just a fifth of Middlebury's cost, but that is still \$3,100 or more per student.^[37] For many families, this is a possible avenue to help their child learn at least a basic level of proficiency in their desired language, but for many others, it is a luxury that cannot be reasonably afforded. If cheapness is what matters most, then it would only make sense to continue on our current path.

The current method of language education in the United States is, if it is even offered, miserably ineffective at a large scale. According to the American Academy of Arts and Sciences, just 21.5% of High School students in the United States learn a second language through their public schooling despite the fact that nearly 90% of high schools offer language education. Additionally, only 16.3% of those who have become fluent in a second language did so through schooling.^[38] It would cost nothing to not change anything, but it would mean that the share of Americans with second language proficiency would continue to be miserably low. That is not to mention the fact that it would be unbearably low in mission critical languages.

If the Cadillac, sure thing, is too expensive, and the cheap and easy option is too ineffective, what would be the proper middle ground? The key is to expand existing infrastructure. If the majority of American kids are not taking foreign language courses, make them. When one thinks of countries with fantastic, near universal, language education, Europe tends to come to mind. Every single EU country, England, Northern Ireland, and Norway require at least 1 foreign language as part of their school curriculum; the United States does not. So many other highly developed liberal democracies simply require their students to reach a certain, realistic, level of proficiency to graduate high school. In fact, language education in most of these countries begins in elementary school.^[39] Fewer than 25% of American elementary schools have a language program or language faculty at all.^[40] There does not need to be a dramatic change in policy beyond expanding what currently exists and making success in learning language consequential in the way that learning Math or History are consequential to a student's ability to graduate. It would also be important to focus on the establishment of Mandarin, Russian, Farsi, Korean, and Arabic programs in areas of high diaspora to produce a linguistically capable next generation in our intelligence services.

³⁶ Middlebury Language Schools, "Chinese Immersion Program Dates and Fees"

³⁷ Concordia Language Villages, "Language Immersion | Summer Camp | High School Credit"

³⁸ American Academy of Arts and Sciences, "The State of Languages in the US..." 8,11.

³⁹ Devlin, "Learning a Foreign Language is a 'Must' in Europe, Not so in America"

⁴⁰ American Academy of Arts and Sciences, "The State of Languages in the US..." 9.

The United States is falling behind with regards to language because we do not place a high enough emphasis on the subject during the formative educational years. This creates a strategic disadvantage for our intelligence services who must operate against foreign adversaries without enough personnel fluent in these adversaries' native languages. The solution to this problem is to put as much emphasis on language learning as our adversaries and allies in order to propagate a generation of proficient Americans who are up to the task of protecting the country against foreign adversaries.